

Corrigendum to “Effects of dust particle sphericity and orientation on their gravitational settling in the Earth’s atmosphere” [Journal of Aerosol Science 150 (2020) 105634]

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The authors regret that Eq. (42) in their paper contains an error and needs to be corrected. The valid expression is:

$$A_{p,y} = \pi ab = \pi \frac{a^2}{\varepsilon}$$

As a consequence, Eq. (50) needs to be rewritten as:

$$Re_y = \left[1 + 0.2415 (K_y Re_y)^{0.687} \right] = \frac{2(\rho_p - \rho_{air}) \rho_{air} a^3 g \sin(\theta)}{9 \varepsilon \mu^2 K_y}$$

The above corrections influence the settling velocity calculation of horizontally oriented particles ($\theta = 90^\circ$). Specifically, the horizontal orientation leads to higher settling velocities than the vertical one ($\theta = 0^\circ$). The corrected results are consistent with Fig. 5 of the paper, where the drag coefficient of horizontally oriented particles is less than the drag coefficient of vertically oriented ones. This means that horizontally oriented particles experience less drag force than their vertical oriented counterparts, and are expected to fall faster.

The sections and figures that are influenced by this correction are:

3.2. Settling velocity of non spherical particles

Vertically oriented particles ($\theta = 0^\circ$) have lower settling velocities than horizontally oriented particles ($\theta = 90^\circ$), as can be seen in Fig. C8a. The relative difference between the velocities can reach the value of $\sim 23\%$ for particles with $D = 10 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. C8b).

Fig. C9 shows the dependence of the settling velocity, v_∞ , on the altitude, H , for vertically and horizontally oriented spheroids with aspect ratio $\varepsilon = 1.4$. The figure contains the corrected calculation in the case of horizontally oriented particles, but the conclusions are the same as described in the original article.

Fig. C10 shows the dependence of the settling velocity, v_∞ , on the aspect ratio, ε , for different orientations of the dust particles, assuming that they are located right above the ground. The corrected calculations in the case of the horizontally oriented particles (Fig. C10b), show that as the aspect ratio increases from 1.4 to 2.4 the decrease in the velocity does not exceed the value of 25% (Fig. 10c). Moreover, Fig. 10c shows that the velocity of vertically oriented particles is more sensitive to the change of the aspect ratio than the velocity of horizontally oriented particles.

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Fig. C8. Dependence of v_∞ on orientation angle, θ , at STP: (a) v_∞ for vertically ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and horizontally ($\theta = 90^\circ$) oriented prolate spheroids with $\epsilon = 1.4$ as a function of the particle polar diameter D , and (b) relative difference (%) between the v_∞ for vertically and horizontally oriented prolate spheroids.

Fig. C9. Dependence of v_∞ on altitude H : (a) v_∞ at different altitudes H for vertically ($\theta = 0^\circ$) oriented prolate spheroids as a function of the particle polar diameter D , (b) v_∞ at different altitudes H for horizontally ($\theta = 90^\circ$) oriented prolate spheroids as a function of the particle polar diameter D , and (c) relative difference (%) between the v_∞ at altitudes 6 and 0 km.

Fig. C10. Dependence of v_∞ on aspect ratio ϵ : (a) v_∞ for different values of ϵ for vertically ($\theta = 0^\circ$) oriented prolate spheroids as a function of the particle polar diameter D , (b) v_∞ for different values of ϵ for horizontally ($\theta = 90^\circ$) oriented prolate spheroids as a function of the particle polar diameter D , and (c) relative difference (%) between the v_∞ for $\epsilon = 1.4$ and $\epsilon = 2.4$.

3.3. Comparison between spherical and non spherical particles

Fig. C11 shows the relative difference (%) as a function of particle polar diameter, D , between the v_∞ in the case of prolate spheroids with different aspect ratios, ϵ , and orientation angles, θ , and the v_∞ of a sphere, at altitudes right above the ground (Fig. C11a), at $H = 6$ km (Fig. C11b), and at $H = 12$ km (Fig. C11c). The negative sign in the plots indicate that the velocities of the prolate spheroids are smaller than the velocities of the spheres.

The correction in the terminal velocities of horizontally oriented particles in this Section, do not alter the conclusions and the mechanisms explained in the original article. The only modification is that the relative difference between the velocities of a sphere and a horizontally oriented prolate spheroid are less sensitive to the change of size and aspect ratio (it does not exceed the value of 30%), as opposed to the relative difference between the velocities of a sphere and a vertically oriented prolate spheroid, that can reach the value of $\sim 65\%$.

Fig. C11. Relative difference (%) between the v_{∞} in the case of spherical particles and in the case of prolate spheroids with different aspect ratios ϵ , orientation angles θ , and at different altitudes H : (a) the particles are located right above the ground at STP, (b) the particles are located at $H = 6$ km, and (c) the particles are located at $H = 12$ km.

4.1. Residual time in the atmosphere

The correction in the calculation of the horizontally oriented particles terminal velocities do not alter the main conclusions and the discussion in this Section. The corrected values are presented in Fig. C12, and Table C1. The only modification in the original article is that the vertically oriented particles stay longer in the atmosphere than the horizontally oriented particles and spherical particles.

Fig. C12. $\langle v_{\infty} \rangle$ as a function of particle polar diameter D for different particle shapes, aspect ratios ϵ , and orientation angles θ calculated at different initial altitudes H . For every case, the $\langle v_{\infty} \rangle$ that is required for the residing time in the atmosphere to be 5 days and 10 days is marked with green line.

Maximum diameter D_{\max} for particles with different shapes, aspect ratios ϵ , and orientation angles θ that remain in the atmosphere for a period of T_{resid} days located at $t = 0$ s at altitude H_{init} km.

T_{resid} (days)	H_{init} (km)	D_{\max} (μm)				
		Sphere	Ellipse		$\epsilon = 2.4$	
			$\epsilon = 1.4$	$\theta = 90^\circ$		$\theta = 0^\circ$
5	1	5.34	6.55	5.73	9.32	6.55
	2	7.55	9.27	8.1	13.2	9.28
	3	9.22	11.32	9.9	16.13	11.34
	4	10.61	13.03	11.39	18.57	13.05
	5	11.81	14.51	12.69	20.68	14.53
	6	12.88	15.83	13.84	22.56	15.84
10	1	3.75	4.6	4.02	6.53	4.6
	2	5.31	6.51	5.7	9.27	6.52
	3	6.48	7.96	6.96	11.34	7.97
	4	7.46	9.16	8.01	13.05	9.17
	5	8.31	10.2	8.92	14.53	10.21
	6	9.06	11.13	9.73	15.85	11.14

4.2 Shape induced gravitational sorting

The correction in the calculation of the horizontally oriented particles terminal velocities leads to the following modifications in the discussion of this section.

First of all, spheroidal particles fall slower than spherical of the same size because they are lighter. The corrected Table C1 provided above, shows that regardless the orientation of the particle, prolate spheroids that stay in the atmosphere the same time with their spherical counterparts are lighter.

Secondly, Fig. C13 shows that in the case of prolate spheroids with the same volume as their spherical counterparts, and in the range of the examined aspect ratios ($1.4 \leq \epsilon \leq 2.4$), the spheroids fall faster than the spheres, regardless their orientation. Moreover, vertically oriented particles fall slower than horizontally oriented ones. Finally, as the aspect ratio increases, the terminal velocity of the prolate spheroids increases.

It can be concluded that in the range of aspect ratios $1.4 \leq \epsilon \leq 2.4$, if the parameter of interest is the size, then the prolate spheroids fall slower than their spherical counterparts of the same size, regardless the particle orientation, since they are lighter. If the parameter of interest is the mass, then the prolate spheroids fall faster than their spherical counterparts of the same mass, regardless the orientation. In any case, there is a shape induced gravitational sorting.

Fig. C13. Relative difference (%) between the $\langle v_{\infty} \rangle$ in the case of spherical particles and in the case of their prolate spheroidal counterparts of the same mass, with different aspect ratios ϵ , orientation angles θ , initially located at altitude $H_{\text{init}} = 6$ km.

5. Summary and conclusions

The conclusions of the original article hold, with the following exception. The particle orientation that leads to higher residual times in the atmosphere is the vertical one ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and not the horizontal ($\theta = 90^\circ$) that was mentioned in the original article.

The authors would like to apologise for any inconvenience caused.